

*Campgate Bronzes and Roman Fire Signalling*¹

The fourth century so called campgate bronze reverses and their turrets have relatively recently been interpreted as depicting signal towers and the ‘turrets’ actually being some kind of beacon.² This is the most recent interpretation but there have been others; they have been interpreted as soldiers or statues of eagles or the Caesars.³ One thing seems clear however; the seemingly intractable label of campgates does not fit. Surviving Roman camp gates do not resemble the structure represented on these reverses. In most cases these campgates have double gates⁴ and the gatehouse is usually bordered by protruding towers.⁵

The coins on the other hand depict a block structure with varying decorations and details.⁶ On some, the doors are indicated; on most the door is merely an opening. Some are simple block structures; some have other decorations on some blocks. Rows of blocks generally vary from six to eleven. On top of the block are two, three, or four

¹ This is a slightly revised version of a paper delivered at the ASCS XXV Conference on February 2nd 2004. I wish to thank all those who commented and provided feedback; their suggestions have been most helpful. I also wish to thank Dr Peter Brennan for his generous and erudite guidance and Professor Ian Plant for inviting me to submit it to CLASSICVM. Any errors or omissions which remain are mine alone.

² The first to make this interpretation seems to have been John F. Fox *Roman Coins and How to Collect Them* (London and New York, 1983), p. 81, quoted by Victor Failmezger ‘Research leads to reinterpretation of “turrets” on Roman bronze campgate reverses’ *The Celator* 5.3 (1991), pp. 14-17, at p. 14 n.7. For images of this type see *RIC* VI, VII and IX and *LRBC*. Some wonderful images can be found at www.beastcoins.com/Architecture/Campgate.htm.

³ Ramsay MacMullen *Constantine* (London, 1969) Plate VII, interprets them as statues of the Caesars. The example that he uses for this explanation is worn enough that the interpretation is plausible on this particular coin but it is not applicable to the whole type. The structures are clearly not statues of any sort on better examples. *RIC* VI (Nicomedia) 24 interprets the dots above the ‘turrets’ as eagles.

⁴ See Roger Wilson *Roman Forts* (London, 1980) and Stephen Johnson *Late Roman Fortification* (London, 1983), especially pp. 16-25.

⁵ It seems clear that the turret interpretation would see these structures as the top part of towers which they patently are not. There is no attempt on the block to depict protruding towers which are represented on other types and which die makers must have been familiar with.

⁶ This description is adapted from Failmezger ‘Research’ and Doug Smith ‘Campgates. A Popular Coin of the Constantinian Period’, at www.ancientcoinmarket.com/ds/featured/campgate/1.html.

turrets or beacons; two being most common. An eight pointed star normally appears between the two ‘turrets’ on those examples.⁷ Dots may occur in the doorway and over the turrets although in most examples the dots above the turrets are connected to them by what seems to be a vertical pole or shaft.⁸

The earliest examples of this type are Diocletianic and date to approximately 296.⁹ Others date to 298 or 299 and show a three dimensional structure similar to the camp sacrifice reverses – although it is clearly not the same structure.¹⁰ Camp sacrifice reverses occur with the tetrarchy from 294 onwards.¹¹ This design is more complicated but continued to be used (although rarely) into the period when campgates also occur.¹² There were earlier representations of protruding towers which die makers could have called upon if the campgate was intended to display such towers but they did not.¹³ It has been argued that the flatter two dimensional campgate reverse was a development and simplification of the camp sacrifice type¹⁴

⁷ Six pointed stars also occur but they are rare. Stars also occur in some three turreted examples.

⁸ There are anomalous types which confound such a generalised description; campgates with obvious towers, turrets, and those which project more tripod turrets around the rear of the camp (see for example *RIC* VI (Ticinum) 8 – 10; (Roma) 5a – 8b). These types should be regarded as anomalous because the vast majority of campgate types fit the description already given. There are no extraneous details that might lead to a different interpretation. Nonetheless it is easy to see why earlier scholars and collectors described campgates as such. Unless you were familiar with Roman signal towers (which we still are not) you could not but describe the type as a campgate.

⁹ See *RIC* VI (Antioch) 35a.

¹⁰ See for example *RIC* VI (Roma) 7a. See n. 15 below. That the structure is different from the camp sacrifice types see *RIC* VI p. 281 n.3.

¹¹ See *RIC* VI (Roma) 19b and 30b; (Treveri) 103b and 117a; (Ticinum) 13b.

¹² See Vagi/HCRE 2822 for a camp sacrifice coin of Galerius (Augustus 305-311). In this example the depiction of protruding towers seem far clearer.

¹³ See Sear *GIC* 3652v for an AE26 example of a gate with protruding towers from the reign of Gordian III 238-244. For many unpublished types which predate the campgate issues see also www.beastcoins.com/Architecture/CityGates/Citygate.htm and <http://citygate.ancients.info/index.htm>. See also *RIC* VII (Trier) 1 for a coin of the city gate with clear protruding towers. Such depictions of provincial city gates should put paid to any notion that the ‘campgate’ also depicted these structures. There are, however, close similarities to the camp sacrifice structures which unfortunately there is not the space here to examine.

¹⁴ M. R. Alföldi ‘Providentia Augusti. To the question of Limes fortification in the fourth century’, *Acta Antiqua Academiae Scientiarum Hungaricae* 3 (1955), pp. 245-259, at 256.

but this seems unlikely as the two types stress different nuances of the virtues and ideologies of their legends and, they can be shown to depict clearly different structures.¹⁵ The context of the signal tower interpretation of these reverses should be sought in relation to the frontiers and reassurances of protection.¹⁶

It is possible that the campgate was a deliberate move away from the three dimensional camp sacrifice coin depictions so that no confusion between the two types could arise. One reason for confusion in modern designation is possibly that a tower or camp in modern conception would be expected to have crenellations and the structures atop the towers in these reverses conform to such a preconception although on closer examination they do not appear at all like battlements. The campgate type remains virtually formally consistent from Diocletian onwards – the only differences being those already noted – the number of ‘turrets’ and the form of the tower. There is an unique, unpublished example, possibly of Licinius II, which depicts a three dimensional tower in orthographic projection which clearly shows that this structure (with ‘turrets’ at each corner) is not (and possibly therefore implies that all campgates are not) any type of camp but a stand alone tower or fort like construction.¹⁷ Campgates were produced profusely during two periods: the reigns of Licinius and Constantine and their sons and especially 316-319 and then 324-330 by Constantine. The initial Licinian issues may coincide with the war with Constantine in 316-317 but the origins of the quarrel remain obscure and so any firm connection remains unknown. Similarly the Constantinian issues from 324 partially coincide with the second war between the two emperors. It may have been considered necessary at these times to make reassurances about the frontier. We are scantily informed but the

¹⁵ However, some examples of camp sacrifice coins do have the legend *Providentiae Aug.* See *RIC VI* (Roma) 10a – 13, 30a – b, 34a – 35b; (Siscia) 33a – b, 54a – b; (Nicomedia) 18, 21, 24; (Cyzicus) 4; (Antiochia) 31; (Alexandria) 7a – b. There also seems to be some kind of transitional type whereby the ‘camp’ was continued behind although without the four princes. See *RIC VI* (Ticinum) 8 – 11b and (Roma) 5a – 8b. The majority of these have the legend *Virtus Militum* although Roma 5a – 6b have *Povidentia Augg.* There is one unique unpublished coin of Licinius II which depicts a three dimensional tower in orthographic projection which clearly shows that this structure (with ‘turrets’ at each corner) is not (and possibly therefore implies that all campgates are not) any type of camp but a stand alone tower.

¹⁶ See below.

¹⁷ See www.ancients.info/forums/showthread.php?threadid=55

Anonymi Valesiani refers to the Goths breaking through the neglected frontiers when Constantine was at Thessalonica after the first civil war.¹⁸ The Gothic incursion shows that the frontiers were threatened at the time and possibly that the state of their protection was part of Imperial propaganda at this time. The peace between Licinius and Constantine after 317 may have led to the joint issues to reassure the empire that the frontiers were being protected. Again, after the second civil war in 324 the *Anonymi* refers to Constantine making war on the Goths.¹⁹

At the end of the fourth century the coin type seems to return under Magnus Maximus and Theodosius although there are now clear protruding towers and the legend became most commonly *Gloria Romanorum* or *Spes Romanorum*.²⁰ The similarities may only be superficial – these could equally be a return to coins like that of Gordian. Nonetheless there have been arguments that the ‘campgate’ reverse continued to influence coin design into the Carolingian Empire.²¹

The signal beacon interpretation is attractive and seems to be far more plausible than the others thus far presented; but other than theory and hypothesis and some vague correlation to frontier defence there seems to have been little more to commend it.

One source which has not been associated with campgates by modern authors until very recently is Sextus Julius Africanus’ *Kestoi* 77.²² This is peculiar because the passage seems to describe a fire signalling system which could pertain exactly to the campgate coin type.

¹⁸ *Anonymi Valesiani Pars Prior* 5.21. It is possible that this neglect arose because of Licinius’ appointment of Valens, the Dacian frontier commander (*ducem limitis*), as Caesar. A large force was gathered at Adrianople and thus presumably the frontier was denuded of troops and this possibly provided a reason for the initial coin issue.

¹⁹ *Anonymi Valesiani Pars Prior* 6.31.

²⁰ Some examples have *Gloria Reipublicae*.

²¹ See ‘Roman Campgates and Carolingian Gates (with an English Addendum)’ at <http://acasun.eckerd.edu/~oberhot/campgate.htm>. The English addendum is a coin of the Anglo-Saxon king, Edward (899-924).

²² However, see now Victor “Tory” Failmezger *Roman Bronze Coins. From Paganism to Christianity 294-364 A. D.* (2002), 108-109. I wish to thank the author for bringing his work to my attention and sending me copies of the relevant pages.

However, before embarking on an examination of how campgates possibly relate to fire signalling, a few introductory remarks on ancient fire signalling are required. This examination is restricted to fire signalling alone although other signalling is highly important especially for understanding how the signal stations possibly depicted on the campgate reverses conducted signalling during daylight hours.

D. J. Woolliscroft's recent *Roman Military Signalling* contains an appendix of ancient sources relating to signalling.²³ The sources for fire signalling itself start with Homer and cover famous passages in Aeschylus, Herodotus, Polybius etc; in fact the sources for Greek fire signalling are more abundant than those for Roman.

Most of the ancient fire signalling source material give the content of a particular message (and sometimes only vaguely); in only a few cases are we given any details of how a signal was transmitted. What is more, several of these sources are poetic and their interpretation debated and controversial.²⁴ Others are inevitably confused, written by men who did not operate the systems they try to describe, or who received information at second hand or greater remove and thus may inadvertently distort or misreport their material.

Nonetheless, the complexity of some of the messages reportedly relayed by fire signals is striking. In some we have the basic single fire or smoke signal which delivered a pre-arranged signal such as 'danger' or 'help'. An excellent example of such a system 'in practice' (and one that reminded the author of Aeschylus' *Agamemnon*) can be seen in the last instalment of Peter Jackson's *The Lord of the Rings* trilogy, *The Return of the King*. Aeschylus refers to waiting for fire signals as

²³ D. J. Woolliscroft *Roman Military Signalling* (Stroud, 2001), pp. 159-171. Some later sources are also included in P. Southern 'Signals Versus Illumination on Roman Frontiers', *Britannia* 21 (1990), 233-242. See also G. H. Donaldson 'Signalling Communications and the Roman Imperial Army', *Britannia* 19 (1988), 349-356.

²⁴ Homer *Iliad* 18.207; Aeschylus *Agamemnon* lines 7-9, 20-9, 278-316. Discussion of the *Agamemnon* passages can be found in W. M. Calder 'The Geography of the Beacon Passage in the *Agamemnon*', *The Classical Review* 36 (1922), pp. 155-159 and J. H. Quincey 'The Beacon-sites in the *Agamemnon*', *Journal of Hellenic Studies* 83 (1963), pp. 118-132.

waiting for a new star;²⁵ the association is a natural one and a possible explanation for the star depicted on Constantinian issues.²⁶ A star would also seem to be the natural choice for depicting fire on coins. However, in many cases the message transmitted by fire signals seems to have been more complicated and must have involved some sort of system or code. The complexity of some messages is only alluded to; such as news of the naval victory of the Greeks against the Persians at Sciathos being sent to Artemisium in 480 BC,²⁷ or that the Athenians were informed of the Peloponnesians sailing to Sestos in 402 BC.²⁸ There are some messages where the system in place must have been more sophisticated and where the signal could not have been pre-arranged since it had to send event-specific information. Tiberius had a squadron of ships to evacuate him from Capri at the time of Sejanus' arrest and had arranged fire signals to 'give news of whatever was to come'.²⁹ Admittedly this message could have been simply 'success' or 'failure', or it could have been more complicated. Thucydides 3.80 tells of the Peloponnesians being told by fire signal that 'a 60-strong squadron of Athenian warships was approaching from the direction of Leucas.' Woolliscroft doubts that the message carried all this information but as Thucydides had been a general at Amphipolis he presumably would have known what signals of the time were capable of.³⁰ This last incident occurred in 427 BC and so it seems that complicated signal systems had been in place well before the Roman period. In the Second Punic War Polybius states that Phillip V of Macedon was kept informed of what was happening in Phocis and Boeotia by fire signal.³¹ And Caesar was informed that Pompey was advancing on the camp of Marcellinus at Dyrrachium in 48 BC during the Civil War.³²

²⁵ *Agamemnon*, lines 7-9.

²⁶ The star is however a very Constantinian motif and could represent Sol or Constantine's victory over Licinius.

²⁷ Herodotus *Histories* 7.183.

²⁸ Thucydides 7.102.

²⁹ Suetonius *Tiberius* 65.

³⁰ Thucydides 3.80.

³¹ Polybius *Histories* 10.42.7. Polybius considers that these were pre-arranged signals. See below.

³² Caesar *The Civil Wars* 2.65.

Polybius himself realised the limitations of fire signalling but he also traced the history of their development and provides evidence of two alternative systems. One earlier system involved two earthenware vessels filled with water and drilled so that the water would flow out at the same rate in both. These were then stoppered and placed at their stations. Several pre-arranged signals were then allocated spaces on rods which were attached to corks which were then floated in the vessels. When one of the messages was required a torch was raised at the first station and the second station replied by also raising a torch. Once both torches were raised the corks would be removed in both places. Once the corresponding message was reached, the first torch would be lowered and both vessels stoppered. Thus the message intended would show on both rods.³³ This system seems very complicated and prone to error but it could, no doubt, have been useful and efficient with practice. The second system which Polybius describes as the latest, and one which he claims to have refined, involved 10 torches (divided into two groups of five; a left and a right) and dividing the alphabet into five parts of five letters each except for the last group which would have only four letters.³⁴ The torch on the left was lifted first to signal which letter group and then that on the right to signal which letter in the group. Thus if the first letter was *kappa*, it belongs to the second group so two torches are raised on the left. Five torches are then raised on the right since it is the fifth letter in the group. This system was capable of messages such as ‘100 Cretans have deserted us’ although Polybius wisely advises economy of expression.³⁵

Polybius’ observations on the limitations of fire signalling are worth quoting in full because they raise issues which his own 10-torch system sought to solve.³⁶

³³ Polybius *Histories* 10.44.1-45.2. This is very similar to the system described by Philon *Mechanica* 7.8.55-57 but written the century before Polybius.

³⁴ Polybius states that this system was invented by Cleoxenus and Democleitus but was refined by himself, presumably when he was Hipparch of the Achaean Confederacy before the battle of Pydna in 168 BC.

³⁵ Polybius *Histories* 10.45.6-47.4. Adam Hart-Davis presented David Woolliscroft’s recreation of both these systems on BBC 2’s ‘What the Romans Did for Us’, the second using flags. See Phillip Wilkinson *What The Romans Did for Us* (London, 2000), pp. 76-79.

³⁶ Polybius *Histories* 10.43.1-10. Polybius seems of the opinion that only pre-arranged signals had existed until very recently.

I don't think I can continue without a full discussion of fire signalling, which is now of the greatest military value, but which used to have major shortcomings. Timing is obviously important for success in any matter, but especially in war, and fire signals are the most efficient means of helping us. They can tell us what has only just happened or even what is currently happening and, with them, anyone who wishes can be kept informed even at a range of three, four, or more day's travel. Help can thus be summoned by signal surprisingly quickly when needed. At one time, fire signals were just beacons, and so were frequently of only limited use to their users. For they could only be used for pre-arranged signals and as real events are unpredictable, they could generally not be communicated by fire-signals. If we take the example I have just mentioned [Phillip V above], one could send news that a fleet had arrived at Oreus, Peparethus or Chalcis, once one had arranged the relevant signals, but one could still not use fire signals to say that some of the inhabitants had changed sides, or been guilty of treachery, or that a massacre had happened in the town, or anything else of this nature. This sort of thing happens often but cannot be anticipated and it is generally the unexpected events which demand fast decisions and responses. Yet it was here that the earlier system broke down, because it is impossible to agree on a signal for what one cannot foresee.

It is clear that the usefulness and limitations of current fire-signalling techniques had been recognised. However, Polybius' account casts doubt on the message recorded by Thucydides at 3.80 although it would seem highly unlikely that the contents of the signal he records could have been pre-arranged. It is possible that Polybius exaggerates the limitations of fire signalling before the system he had a hand in modifying and thus overplays his own importance. Nonetheless his 10-torch system represents a solution (possibly a very early one) to the problems he identifies and further systems and modifications will have continued.

Sextus Julius Africanus in his *Kestoi* mentions a signalling system. Julius Africanus is a famous Christian chronographer of the early to mid third century AD and whether he is the same as the author of the *Kestoi* is debated. However, Julius Africanus seems

to have flourished in the period AD 220-245 and the *Kestoi* was dedicated to the emperor Severus Alexander (who reigned AD 222-245).³⁷ Therefore the works were contemporary and it is possible they were written by the same man.³⁸ In *Kestoi* 77 Africanus includes this observation:

The Romans have the following technique which seems to me to be amazing. If they want to communicate something by fire signal, they make the signals so: they select places that are suitable for making fire signals. They divide the fires into a right, a left and a middle fire so that they read *alpha* to *theta* from the left-hand one, *iota* to *pi* from the middle one and *rho* to *omega* from the right-hand fire. If they signal *alpha*, they raise up the fire signal on the left once, for *beta* twice and for *gamma* three times. If they signal *iota* they raise the middle fire once, for *kappa* twice and for *lambda* thrice, and if they want to signal *rho*, *sigma* or *tau*, they raise the right-hand signal once, twice or three times. In this way should you want to signal *rho* you do not need to raise hundreds of fire signals, but only one with the right-hand torch. Those who receive the signals then de-code them in the same way, or pass them on to the next station.

Africanus is the only ancient author to refer to such a system.³⁹ The system he describes could equally well be applied to the Latin alphabet although it is odd that

³⁷ Jules Africain *Fragments des Cestes. Provenant de la Collection des Tacticiens Grecs* J.-R. Vieillefond (ed.) (Paris 1932), xiii and xvi. See also E. L. Wheeler 'Why the Romans can't defeat the Parthians: Julius Africanus and the Strategy of Magic', *Roman Frontier Studies 1995*, eds. W. Groenman-van Waateringe, B. L. van Beek, W. J. H. Willems and S. L. Wynia (Oxford, 1997), pp. 575-579, at 575-576. Wheeler's projected work arguing that the first nine books of the *Kestoi* were presented to Severus in Spring 231 when the emperor departed for the Persian war, has not, to my knowledge, appeared.

³⁸ The debate on Africanus is by no means simple. A good brief introduction to the *Kestoi* can be found in B. Grenfell and A. Hunt (eds.) *The Oxyrhynchus Papyri* III (London, 1903), 412, pp. 36-41. Otherwise see Vieillefond's introduction to Jules Africain *Fragments des Cestes*, vii-lviii; H. Gelzer *Sextus Julius Africanus und die byzantinische Chronographie* (1880-1898); W. Reichardt *Die Briefe des Sextus Julius Africanus an Aristides und Origenes* (1909); and A. Roberts and J. Donaldson *The Ante-Nicene Fathers* (Volume VI, Grand Rapids, 1951), pp. 123-140.

³⁹ See R. J. Forbes *Studies in Ancient Technology*² VI (Leiden, 1966), pp. 171-180, especially 179-180.

Africanus' Romans use Greek letters. The system Africanus describes can be seen as, not only a solution to the issues Polybius raised, but also one which took up, further modified and simplified Polybius' own 10-torch system. It is likely that in the more than 350 years between the two descriptions other systems and refinements were developed or improved.

If we apply this system to the three 'turreted' campgate examples there is a perfect match; three signal beacons per tower for the three sets of eight letters.⁴⁰ Delbrück postulated that the garrison of a signalling station was probably three men,⁴¹ these were, after all, not defensive positions – in the case of the system Africanus describes one man for each signal beacon. Such a garrison would be all that would be required to run such a system efficiently. It looks too good to be true.

The warning has been made above that in some cases ancient authors give confused or distorted accounts, and their information can be second hand or worse. Authors can also provide information which is revelatory for us but which was already centuries old when they inserted it into their own pastiches. The most commonly found assertion for Africanus' composition techniques is that he was uncritical of his sources,⁴² however in this case we have no original with which to compare him.

⁴⁰ It is interesting to note that the star is, in the majority of cases, eight pointed and thus possibly related to the signalling system.

⁴¹ H. Delbrück *History of the Art of War within the Framework of political History II, The Barbarian Invasions* (translated by J. Renfroe, Westport, 1975), p. 154, quoted by Failmezger 'Research', p. 17. Failmezger sees the campgate as relating to a structure similar to the milecastles on Hadrian's Wall (14-15). Rather than this it would be preferable to see them as the turrets on the same wall or signal stations such as that at Scarborough or on the Gask Ridge – however, see below. See Anne S. Robertson 'Roman "Signal Stations" on the Gask Ridge', *Transactions of the Perthshire Society of Natural Science* (Special Issue, 1974), pp. 14-29; R. A. H. Farrar 'Roman signal stations over Stainmore and beyond', in W. S. Hanson and L. J. F. Keppie (eds.) *Roman Frontier Studies XII* (1980), pp. 211-231; and D. J. Woolliscroft 'Signalling and the Design of Hadrian's Wall', *Archaeologia Aeliana* 17 (1989), pp. 5-19.

⁴² Johannes Quasten *Patrology*, Volume 2, *The Ante-Nicene Literature After Irenaeus* (Washington, 1950), p. 139.

Many other passages also suggest Africanus recorded his own observations and it is possible he saw this system in action.⁴³

Even if we take these reservations into consideration, Africanus provides a totally coherent and workable system, and one which seems to marry perfectly with the campgate reverse. It is also no stretch to see Africanus' system as able to operate on a two or four beacon basis (in accordance with the numbers of beacons found on campgate reverses). In the former the alphabet could simply be split into two groups; in the latter into four.⁴⁴ It is quite possible that different systems using two, three, or four beacons were used perhaps depending on the current 'threat' or other such criteria.

Woolliscroft raises a valid concern that in the system Africanus describes only one beacon at a time is lit.⁴⁵ There are no signals which combine two or three signal fires being shown at once. It is possible that Africanus did not include such material or that his source did not. It is probable that such combinations did occur and were part of the communication system which would have evolved and undergone constant field adjustments. It is also possible that simple or non-alphabetic signals were transmitted with two or more beacons shown at once.⁴⁶ Certainly the added complexity of such a

⁴³ See *Fragments des Cestes*, vii-xvii and Wheeler 'Why can't the Romans', 575-576.

⁴⁴ Failmezger, *Roman Bronze Coins*, 108, argues that the two and four beacon systems used a grid of 20 letters (he omits G, U, Y and Z) in four columns akin to Polybius' 10 torch method. He argues that in the two beacon system the left beacon set the row and the right to set the column. For the four beacon system the left hand beacon again signifies the row and then the next beacon lit signifies the column. Failmezger refers (n.214) to similar grid systems used by POWs during the Vietnam War. Such systems were also used by WWII POWs. The use of both systems in the ancient world are speculative but totally plausible.

⁴⁵ Woolliscroft *Roman Military Signalling*, pp. 44-46. One problem would be identifying exactly which of the three signals was being used. Woolliscroft's experiments led to a possible solution whereby all three signals were shown and the one intended to send the signal was momentarily blocked out so that the message was sent by the signal which was 'off' rather than 'on'. It might also be possible that all three signals were shown at the start of transmission to establish their relative positions.

⁴⁶ During the time of the Armada a three beacon system was set up based on the Isle of Wight. One torch meant the coastal stations were alerted but the message relayed no further. Two meant that all coastal stations from Dorset to Sussex alerted troops inland by their own signal and three beacons

system should be no barrier to supposing the Roman system included such procedures. Woolliscroft himself has experimented with the system and suggests 10-12 characters could be sent per minute. This, he suggests, could be increased by use of a Morse code standard whereby more common letters are assigned the least number of flashes.⁴⁷ Such ‘field modifications’ are entirely possible for the Roman period and it is also possible that such information was not known by historians. We are of course dealing with highly sensitive systems and information which could prove disastrous if it fell into the wrong hands. Both Thucydides and Polyaeus tell of the Plataeans lighting fires to confuse and ‘jam’ the fire signals sent by the Spartans to Thebes for reinforcements during the siege of Plataea in 428 BC.⁴⁸ The secrecy which doubtless surrounded military signalling from time immemorial is the reason our sources on signalling are almost uniformly uninformative. It is possible that Africanus saw, or his source provided, the basics of a system but not details of current field practice. In the field these basics would inevitably change and, as the sources show, codes were probably employed.

Whilst I disagree with Woolliscroft’s suggestion that the signals Africanus describes could be 25 metres apart to increase the range, many of his suggestions are useful and show this system could easily have been a working one. He suggests that the useful range of three beacons placed on a Roman signal tower top (approximately 3.5-4.5m across) would have been about 4km. This would have been more than sufficient in most situations.⁴⁹

meant most of southern England was put on readiness for attack. See Southern ‘Signals’, p. 235, and C. G. Cruikshank *Elizabeth’s Army* (1966), pp. 70-71.

⁴⁷ We should assume some kind of proto-morse code operation within the system Africanus describes whereby a space was understood between each signal so that changes in letter could be comprehended especially if the following letter was from the same group or even for double letters. Certainly for numbers such a method for reading signals would allow for little miscomprehension, otherwise signalling ‘three hundred’ (CCC) for instance and even without a code could become confusing, not to mention cumbersome.

⁴⁸ Thucydides 3.22 and Polyaeus *Strategemata* 6.19.2.

⁴⁹ Woolliscroft *Roman Military Signalling*, p. 46. He suggests that some signals had to be made over 10km. Woolliscroft reiterated to me that the signal towers on Hadrian’s Wall do not increase in size even if they had to send messages over a greater distance.

In reality the signalling structures would presumably have had the capability of having signal beacons on more than one side so as to be able to signal in more than one direction.⁵⁰ The author has been unable to discover any archaeological report which mentions the discovery or identification of remains of signalling beacons. The materials of signalling were presumably predominately of wood, pottery and bronze and so perishable, easily broken, reused, or melted and difficult to positively identify given our very limited knowledge of signalling material let alone signalling techniques.

The signalling interpretation of campgates certainly ties in with the legend of *Providentiae Aug(g)* and *Providentiae Caes(s)* common to most of these reverses.⁵¹ *Providentiae* comes from the verb *provideo* which means foresight but also the provision or care appertaining to it.⁵² Under Augustus *Providentia* was the personal quality of the emperor caring for his people; one aspect of which was the security of the frontier. Over the next centuries this frontier association was not common, instead we find *providentia* referring to the security of the succession and the protection of the empire from conspiracies. In the late third and early fourth centuries the protection of the frontier again comes to the fore. Early camp sacrifice coins showing the four princes do have *providentia* legends which certainly suggests the security of succession but, in a military context and, whether because of mounting external pressures and/or internal military or economic problems, Diocletian, Licinius and Constantine once again stressed their care and protection of the empire in respect to the frontier; and their way of demonstrating this care was possibly through a revived or enhanced signalling system which provided protection from and early warning of both external and internal threats. There was no return to *providentia* legends on coins

⁵⁰ This can be seen in the unique coin of Licinius showing all four sides of a signalling tower.

⁵¹ Some have the legend *Virtus Aug*, *Virtus Caes* and *Virtus Militum*.

⁵² See M. P. Charlesworth 'Providentia and Aeternitas', *The Harvard Theological Review* 29 (1936), pp. 107-132; and Alföldi 'Providentia Augusti', pp. 245-259. Alföldi includes many images from a hoard found in Nagytétény which contains mostly campgates. She does not question the campgate interpretation and her argument that the coin design was a natural development and simplification of the earlier almost insurmountably difficult camp sacrifice coins of Diocletian is unnecessary. See also Russell T. Scott 'Providentia Aug.', *Historia* 31 (1982), pp. 436-459.

under Constantine when the succession was an issue.⁵³ It is possible that the frontier reforms of Diocletian included forts with signalling capabilities rather than the signal towers of earlier systems such as Hadrian's wall which, according to Woolliscroft, signalled along the wall to each other until one could signal back to the forts. Thus the coin type possibly stressed both fortification and signalling – otherwise the domination of the reverse by the building rather than depicting just the beacon is difficult to explain.

We should ask why firstly Diocletian and then Licinius and Constantine and their sons wished to commemorate a signal system on their coins if that system was not new. The implication is that the system the new coin type commemorates was also an innovation. This could tie in with the many frontier reforms of Diocletian but why was it taken up so vigorously by his successors and especially in the periods from 316-319 and 324-330? It is possible that they had revived a system that was in existence at the beginning of the third century and possibly combined it with their frontier towers. Other than the Africanus passage and the campgate reverses we have no evidence that such a system existed at the beginning of the third century, was abandoned and was then revived. The introduction or celebration of this system by late third and fourth century emperors was considered worthy enough to revive the message of *providentia* as meaning protection of the frontier. The revival of this nuance of the virtue can also be found in the contemporary *Panegyrici Latini*⁵⁴ and in Zosimus 2.34 where critical reference is made to Constantine's abandonment of Diocletian's *pronoia* in reference to the defence of the frontier. The source of Zosimus' famous passage is most likely to have been the *Universal History* of Eunapius. In the majority of the *Panegyrici Latini* references *providentia* is used in a military context concerning the defence or protection of the empire, although there

⁵³ A Constantinian issue from 326, *RIC* VII (Roma) 275, shows Constantine between his three sons with the legend *Felicitas Romanorum*.

⁵⁴ See C. E. V. Nixon and Barbara Rodgers *In Praise of Roman Emperors. The Panegyrici Latini* (Berkeley, 1994). X (II) *Mamertini Panegyricus* 5.2; VIII (V) *Incerti Panegyricus Constantio Caesari* 4.3 (*providetis*), 6.2, 18.6; IX (IV) *Eumeni Pro Instaurandis Scholis Oratio* 4.1, 8.1, 10.1; VII (VI) *Incerti Panegyricus Maximiano et Constantino Dictus* 7.2; VI (VII) *Incerti Panegyricus Constantino Augusto Dictus* 6.1, 18.3 (*provideras*); V (VIII) *Incerti Gratiarum Actio Constantino Augusto* 2.3, 8.5; XII (IX) *Panegyricus Dictus Constantino Filio Constantii* 3.1 (*providere*), 6.4 (*providens*), 8.3.

are also uses connected with its other meanings of foresight regarding the succession and general foresight for the well being of the empire. It is possible that Licinius and Constantine and their sons, following on from Diocletian, were celebrating creating a more efficient frontier signalling system and therefore enhancing the Augustus' *providentia*. It is also possible that two and four beacon systems – if the coins depict actual different signalling arrangements – were recent improvements.

It is not essential that we interpret the campgate reverses literally in every case – they were produced at every mint and their two, three and four turreted manifestations were spread across all fifteen mints.⁵⁵ The decorative details also differ from example to example regardless of origin. Thus whilst they may represent an actual system and the emperors wish to have it commemorated, it is not necessary to see them as portraits of individual buildings. Such differences may be explained by the artistic licence of individual die makers. Nonetheless it is clear that the type represents something real, even on the broadest interpretation. This presumably would have had to have been instantly recognisable in order that the object and its message were quickly and easily digestible, even if recipients had been nowhere near a frontier or a signalling station. Most people would have been nowhere near a military camp either and yet that image and its corresponding messages were instantly recognisable.

We have little information about the genesis of ancient coin design – who came up with designs and how they were transmitted to the various mints. Presumably the initial spur for a new coin type would have come from reasonably high up in the imperial service to then be passed, possibly with some explanation of their significance, to a senior individual within the senior mint depending on the location. From there however, it is probable that it was passed to the die makers and to other

⁵⁵ See Alföldi 'Providentia Augusti', pp. 246-247. The 316-319 issue are mainly Eastern although there are issues from Western mints and in Constantine's name. Even before the war in 324 Licinius coins were not struck in Constantinian mints but after the war they were struck in all mints. Still they were more common in Eastern mints – possibly because they required more reassurance of continued protection. According to Alföldi, after 328 campgates were superseded, first by *Constantiniana Dafne* types which celebrated Constantine's camp building on the Lower Danube and then by smaller *Gloria Exercitus* bronzes. The replacement of campgates with similar building program and military issues might suggest that they too should be viewed in a military and building program context.

mints with possibly little more than written instruction or perhaps a drawing or example coin.

What is more, it is clear that the ‘campgate’ coins were intended to signify and communicate something to the people of the empire. They were also intended to convey the same message for a concentrated and extended period of time. The signalling interpretation, and its combination with *providentia*, provides a more plausible interpretation of that message than that which maintains that these are simply the gates of military camps or of provincial cities. Other, instantly recognisable, depictions of camps were available and they were not associated necessarily with *providentia*. Whilst this does not preclude such an association, frontier signalling and thus protection was less likely to have had complicating connotations. *Kestoi 77* does not provide all the answers to the possibility of Roman military signalling depicted on campgates but, as has been argued, it provides a perfectly workable and plausible system which fits the design of the type without any stretch of argument or credibility. We may therefore have to consider renaming the type.